

Can London Still Accommodate the Next Generation of Young Graduates?

Candidate Number: 2425SUN14

Department of Architecture
University of Cambridge

Word Count (excluding captions & bibliography): 8,752 words

This dissertation is submitted for

Part II Dissertation

April 2025

Acknowledgements

Completing this dissertation has made me realize how fortunate I have been to receive invaluable support from Cambridge. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Professor Ying Jin, for his insightful guidance and prompt responses throughout my research. I am deeply thankful to Professor Nicholas Bullock for his intellectual generosity and all the inspiring discussions. My appreciation also goes to Dr. Felipe Hernández for his consistent encouragement and understanding. Finally, I wish to extend my appreciation to Dr. Jinze Sha, who truly excelled in guiding me to excel in Excel.

Abstract

Young graduates - those who come from universities, colleges and other further education and are traditionally inspired by London jobs – are finding the city’s accommodation well beyond reach. This dissertation investigates how London has been changing in the recent decade. My research first reviews the predicament for the young graduates; next, Census 2011 and 2021 data are analysed to track shifts in young adult populations; this is then compared against housing stock changes by unit size and location, with case studies of what is happening on the ground. The findings reveal a clear structural challenge that has escaped most researchers in the field: London’s young adult population group aged 25-34, of which the young graduates belong, is actually declining in most areas, while housing construction is now skewed towards larger or high-end units for older, wealthier families. This means London appears to be pricing out its next generation of young graduates and this catastrophic trend demands strong policy intervention and innovative design solutions.

Table of contents

List of figures	ix
1 Housing predicaments for the new generation	3
1.1 Bank of Mum and Dad	4
1.2 Universities, Workplaces and Charities	6
1.3 Government Interventions	7
1.4 Lack of understanding of the current situation in London	9
2 The Impact of Covid-19 and Shifting Demographics	11
2.1 Evaluating the Reliability of Census under COVID-19	12
2.2 Structural Shift, Not a Pandemic Glitch	13
3 Spatial Distribution of Young Adults vs. Housing Stock (2011-2021)	15
3.1 Age Group 20-24	16
3.1.1 Overview	16
3.1.2 2011 Distribution	17
3.1.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021	19
3.2 Age Group 25-34	20
3.2.1 Overview	20
3.2.2 2011 Distribution	20
3.2.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021	22
3.3 Age Group 35-44	23
3.3.1 Overview	23
3.3.2 2011 Distribution	23
3.3.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021	25
3.4 Age Group 45-54 and 55-64	26

3.4.1	Overview	26
3.4.2	2011 Distribution	26
3.4.3	Patterns and Changes in 2021	29
3.5	Age 65 and Above	30
3.5.1	Overview	30
3.5.2	2011 Distribution	31
3.5.3	Patterns and Changes in 2021	32
4	Can London still accommodate young people with suitable housing?	35
4.1	One-Bedroom Units 2011	36
4.2	Spatial Misalignment for 1-bedroom Units	37
4.3	Two-Bedroom Units in 2011	38
4.4	Limited Alignment with 25-34	39
4.5	Three-Bedroom Units in 2011	40
4.6	Four and more Bedroom Units	43
4.7	Good News? Lots of 4-beds are built	44
5	Structural Failures in London's Housing Market for the New Generation	47
5.1	Self-Regulated Market v.s. Social Needs	47
5.2	Policy and Planning Shortcomings	48
5.3	Bottlenecks in the planning process	49
5.4	Consequences: Young Londoners' Coping Strategies	50
6	Conclusions	57
6.1	Potential interventions for a more responsive housing system	57
6.2	Summary and future work	59
	References	61

List of figures

1.1	Total Number of Dwellings in London by Period of Construction(1900-2024)	9
1.2	Dwelling Completions in London by Tenure Type and Time Period (1990-2024)	10
2.1	Comparison of 2021 Census and Mid-Year Estimates (2021-2023) by Boroughs	12
2.2	Change of Population by Age Band in London, Mid-Year Estimates(2001-2023)	13
2.3	Change in Population Share by Age Band in London, Mid-Year Estimates (2001-2023)	13
3.1	London Tube Fare Zone Transport for London (2025)	16
3.2	Share of age 20-24 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	17
3.3	Share of 20-24 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	18
3.4	Share of 20-24 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	19
3.5	Share of age 25-34 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	20
3.6	Share of 25-34 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	21
3.7	Share of 25-34 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	22
3.8	Share of age 35-44 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	23
3.9	Share of 35-44 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	24
3.10	Share of 35-44 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	25
3.11		26
3.12	Share of 45-54 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	27
3.13	Share of 55-64 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	28
3.14	Share of 45-54 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	29
3.15	Share of 55-64 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	30
3.16	Share of 65+ in Resident Population (a) 2011 (b) 2021	31
3.17	Share of 65+ in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	32
3.18	Share of 65+ in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021	33
3.19	Comparison on Share of Different Age Groups - Difference 2011-2021	34

4.1	Share of 1-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	36
4.2	Share of 1-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	36
4.3	37
4.4	Share of 2-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	38
4.5	Share of 2-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	39
4.6	39
4.7	Share of 3-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	40
4.8	Share of 3-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	41
4.9	Share of 3-Bedroom in All Households- Difference 2011-2021	42
4.10	Share of 4 and More Bedrooms in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021. . . .	43
4.11	Share of 4 and More Bedrooms Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021	43
4.12	44
4.13	Comparison on Share of Different Households - Difference 2011-2021 . . .	45
5.1	Share of age 35-44 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.	50
5.2	Typical 12 sqm studio layout at The Collective Old Oak (The Collective, 2024)	51
5.3	View of World's End Estate in Chelsea, London	53
5.4	Plan of 1, 2, 3 bedroom flats in World's End Estate (Zoopla Limited, 2025b)	53
5.5	Comparison on different house types in World's End Estate and London Housing Guide (Mayor of London, 2010). (Units not meeting modern standards are marked in red. Data based on real-estate listings.)	55

Introduction

For more than a century, London has been a magnet for those who have recently graduated from universities and colleges and look for inspiring jobs. The city is now facing a housing affordability crisis that particularly hits this young graduate cohort. Far more limited housing options, stagnant wages and skyrocketing rents are deterring many young adults of this cohort to work in London. This dissertation is motivated by the question: can London still accommodate the next generation of its young graduates under these conditions?

Chapter 1 provides the background on the housing predicaments of this generation, situating current challenges in historical context. It reviews past policy responses and examines how young graduates today get by precariously. Chapter 2 analyses recent demographic shifts, including the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on where young adults live. Chapter 3 investigates the spatial distribution of London's young adult population and compares it against housing stock changes over the past decade, revealing geographic mismatches between where young people cluster and where new housing is supplied. Chapter 4 evaluates whether London is building the right kinds of homes in the right places for the emerging generation. Then Chapter 5 and Chapter 6 together address the core question and consider what changes are needed for London to accommodate its next generation of young graduates.

Chapter 1

Housing predicaments for the new generation

Over the past century and a half, the UK's housing policy has undergone continuous adjustments, and many of the city's initiatives such as garden suburbs and minimum housing standards have evolved in response to social needs. Palate (2020) noted that the Industrial Revolution and the associated overcrowding and public health crisis has triggered the planning and design of housing to mitigate problems associated with diseases, crime, atheism, drunkenness and social unrest. The two world wars reinforced the idea that providing housing with low cost and high quality was a national responsibility. Substandard housing has returned to London in recent decades along with worsening affordability. In 2008, the then Mayor of London, Boris Johnson said 'It's shameful that new buildings in London have some of the smallest rooms in Europe.' Post Covid-19, the housing crisis that young people are facing a new turning point.

Despite government's efforts in housing reform, the current generation (which is often referred to as Gen Z, although strictly speaking, the Gen Z includes a wider cohort from aged 13 to 28, i.e. born between 1997-2012) is still facing growing challenges in the housing market as they are beginning to enter education, adulthood and employment. Studies have shown that it is harder than ever for this current generation to achieve financial independence. For instance, Spratt (2024) argues 'The housing crisis means adulthood starts at 35 for Gen Z'.

Of course, housing is only part of a larger problem for London's young generation. Soaring living costs, limited job opportunities and stagnant salaries have made it increasingly difficult for them to secure their own housing. For example, a part 1 architectural assistant, a common entry-level role for young architects, earns as little as £24,000 per year pre-tax in London (9B Careers, 2025). Meanwhile, the estimated average annual living cost in London in 2024 was £50,400, more than double that salary (McCallum, 2024).

Rising rent costs have further exacerbated the affordability crisis, creating a widening gap between income and expenses going forward. For instance, London's rent inflation reached 11.5 percent in 2024 (Office for National Statistics, 2025b), while the national average was 9.2 percent. Meanwhile, wages have failed to keep pace with the rising housing costs, as wage growth in 2024 stood at just 5.6 percent (Office for National Statistics, 2025a).

With wages lagging behind rising rents, the unaffordability of housing remains central to the predicament, significantly shaping their living choices. In 2023, 42 percent of individuals aged 15-34 lived with their families, as opposed to 36 percent in 1996 (Office for National Statistics, 2024). Borrett (2024) points out that 'Gen Z are twice as likely as younger millennials to be renting and who pay on average almost half their income on rent.'

The lack of strong overall policy intervention, particularly in affordable housing policies and rental regulations, has left many young adults relying on alternative forms of support. In the absence of effective housing policies, young adults often first turn to parents for financial support, followed by the institutions (e.g. universities and colleges) and workplaces they belong to, with charities and local councils offering limited assistance for this young graduate's age group. The following section reviews how the young graduates are getting housing in London.

1.1 Bank of Mum and Dad

The term 'Bank of Mum and Dad' refers to the financial support young adults receive from their parents, either through direct monetary remittance or inheritance. Young adults have increasingly relied on parental financial support, as housing costs and other expenses rise spectacularly.

Research conducted by LSE indicates the mean parental contribution has doubled in the last two decades (1990-2010), and the average contribution in higher-cost areas such as London has reached £76,290. Among surveyed parents, 50 percent reported helping their children

with a deposit for a home purchase, while 35 percent provided financial support for mortgage payments. This assistance was predominantly given to young adults aged 20-29 and 30-39, with significantly fewer parents offering support to older age groups (Scanlon et al., 2019).

Financial assistance extends beyond home purchases. (Bratley, 2024) found that even non-homebuyers frequently receive lump-sum financial support from parents. In fact, one in every three UK adults reported receiving parental help for day-to-day expenses, with London having the highest percentage (41%) and the most generous average support (£19,275.69 per year).

The gifts come with strings attached - Although parental support is one of the simplest ways to assist young adults, it may not be always sustainable. First, most parents do not operate like banks: they rarely have formal contracts documenting the transactions, nor do they regularly discuss the exact repayments dates. In other words, these transfers are often gifts rather than loans. Nevertheless, Scanlon et al. (2019) survey highlighted that while most parents were pleased to help, nearly half felt it was unfair, believing financial independence should be their children's responsibility.

Consequently, the subsidy might come with certain expectations rather than actual repayment of money. It is described as 'the gifts come with strings attached' (John, 2025). More than half of Gen Z reported that their parent is expecting something in return-not necessarily in monetary form. For example, parents may expect to review their children's entrepreneurial business plans or require unmarried children to purchase property with a partner to sign cohabitation agreements (John, 2025).

Discussion on the sustainability of parental subsidies - While the parent-child intergenerational wealth transfers provide short-term advantages, they are increasingly unsustainable in the long run. The majority of the parents in their 50s and 60s have benefited from low interest rates, generous pension schemes, and massive increases in house prices since when they purchased the properties. The intergenerational wealth transfer is attractive to the parents because they can help the younger generations own housing much earlier, thus able to focus more on their careers and potentially help retain control of family assets (Scanlon et al., 2019).

However, Scanlon et al. (2019) highlight two rising challenges:

- Many parents in their 40s now did not experience the same financial advantages as those in their 50s and 60s, many of them might still be repaying heavy loans when the younger Gen Z cohort need such help.
- As life expectancy is extending, the older generations are increasingly aware of the need to secure their financial ability for later-life care, given the context of world-wide ageing problem and the rising costs of elderly care.

Therefore, while financial transfers from parents will remain an important source of financial support for young adults, they are becoming increasingly unsustainable due to rising financial pressures over time.

1.2 Universities, Workplaces and Charities

Aside from parental help, it would be reasonable to consider possible assistance from institutions-such as universities/colleges, workplaces, and charities-to provide housing support. However, these institutions can only offer limited assistance.

For example, the largest university in London in terms of students' size - University College London (UCL) states that first year undergraduates are prioritised for a place for university accommodation, while the rest may still apply and stand a chance for getting university accommodation (UCL, 2024). A current final-year UCL undergraduate confirmed that, in practice, it is extremely difficult for second- and third-year students to obtain university accommodation, despite being eligible to apply. He also mentioned that first-year university-managed housing in London can cost as little as £245 per week, including utilities and meals, an option almost impossible to find in the private housing market.

Similarly, only first-year undergraduates at Imperial College London (IC) are guaranteed college accommodation. (Imperial College, 2025). One IC student described how, during his first year, he lived in university-provided ensuite accommodation in North Acton for just £170 a week. However, once students move beyond their first year, they must navigate the private rental sector because of the shortage in school accommodation. The same IC student, now a third-year intern at AstraZeneca in Cambridge, receives only £300 weekly as salary from the company and struggles with living costs: during the week, he stays at Travelodge near Cambridge Station, and on weekends he commutes back to London, sharing a £400-per-week apartment in Kensington. The two cases reveal that both universities and workplaces rarely provide substantial housing assistance. While it is understandable that first-year students

require greater housing security, this policy leaves soon-to-graduate students and early-career professionals in a precarious position.

Recognising these housing challenges, UCL also references charities as potential source of housing support. However, by examining the major charities listed (Students' Union UCL, 2024), it is obvious that they are primarily focused on preventing homelessness and providing temporary shelter for individual cases, rather than addressing the broader issue of housing for young renters.

1.3 Government Interventions

Given that universities and charities may only provide assistance in limited cases, the responsibility for ensuring housing conditions has now and historically fallen on council intervention. When there are housing difficulties, government usually has two solutions: mass production of social housing and the introduction of minimum housing standards. As Palate (2020) noted, 'along with the widespread campaign for Homes fit for Heroes, housing would not be resolved solely as a quantitative issue, but also, and most importantly, as a qualitative concern by the state.' These two approaches were initially aimed at reducing post-war housing shortages, and they successfully ensured basic living conditions. However, as societal and economic conditions evolved, both strategies have become increasingly difficult to implement effectively.

The idea of Mass-produced houses is to provide the disadvantaged people with increasing housing supply. However, it is often misconstrued as a direct solution to affordability. The Help to Buy Policies aimed to provide UK's first-time buyers with financial assistance, however served as bigger failure by receiving national-wide criticism. Wolf (2013) strongly opposed the scheme, arguing that this would instead keep housing costly. He wrote:

'a policy of increasing demand is absurd. It may increase supply a little, but only by raising prices still higher than they would otherwise be. If one wanted to increase supply, the solution is evident, but politically unthinkable: make a large quantity of land available for development and impose a swingeing site value tax, to compel building'. Wolf (2013)

There was also the Right to Buy policy (1980) which led to the sale of thousands of council-owned homes at a cut price, yet with very few new replacements built by local authorities. (Malpass, 2005). Nationally, the share of households renting from councils halved from 31% in 1980 to just 16% in 2022/23 (New Economics Foundation, 2024). This seemingly offered

an opportunity for social housing tenants to become homeowners. However, the long-term effect, as Malpass (2005) pointed out:

“On the one hand, the importance attached to the sale of council houses, a policy for changing the ownership of existing dwellings, adding nothing at all to the total stock. And on the other hand, far from promising the electorate so many hundred thousand dwellings each year, Michael Heseltine steadfastly refused to predict how many dwellings would be built. By the early 1980s output targets had ceased to be a measure of ministerial virility and had disappeared from the political agenda. The Government has, however, continued to promote the expansion of home ownership as the cure-all for housing problems”. Malpass (2005)

In the UK, an estimated 41% of homes sold under Right to Buy are now being rented out by private landlords (New Economics Foundation, 2024) - an effective transfer of public assets into the private rental sector. For young Londoners today, this means far fewer inexpensive social homes are available than for previous generations, forcing many into the costlier private rental market or long waits for council housing.

The effort on setting housing standards has also encountered difficulties. If the Tudor Walters Report(1918) and the Dudley Report(1944) represented the government’s early efforts to tackle the problem of post-war housing crisis, the Parker Morris Report(1961) then stands out to be the first to respond to social changes. While the earlier reports set explicit requirements for the mass-produced council houses, the PM report is more complex as it targeted housing type and strategies. First, the PM report was published in the backdrop of rapid social changes, including greater female participation in the workforce, the rise of television and private cars reshaping daily life, higher education levels leading to more people getting university degrees, and the economic prosperity of the 1960s. These social changes rendered previous housing standards outdated Palate (2020). Second, the PM Report regulated private enterprises houses, as it foresaw the future rise of the private rent sector. One last significant progress is the approach of overall recommendations. Instead of setting exact minimum requirements on the area of the room, the PM report provided an overall recommendation, allowing for certain flexibility in practice Palate (2020). The lesson learned from setting such requirements is a forward-thinking mindset, emphasising that housing policies, like urban planning, must anticipate future needs. However, despite its progressive vision, the Parker Morris Standards were eventually abolished, partly due to overly optimistic estimations of housing supply Palate (2020).

Since the abolition of the PM standards, most subsequent housing standards have remained in a grey zone. The Nationally Described Space Standards (Greater London Authority, 2014), the London Housing Design Guide (Mayor of London, 2010), and the London Plan Guidance (Mayor of London, 2023) all have set similar regulations on minimum housing standards, yet they remained largely advisory. The main conflict lies between enforcing minimum standards and maintaining housing supply. In a market already struggling with slow housing delivery and undersupply, imposing mandatory standards will reduce supply even further, thereby exacerbating the situation. The Mayor’s London Plan sets a target of 52,000 new homes per year, yet only 35,000 were delivered last year (Barber, 2024). Across the city, an average of 37,768 new homes were added annually between 2020/21 and 2022/23, but the majority (69%) were for the private market, with just 1,148 completions per year allocated to social rented housing (Barber, 2024). The failure of the plan can be explained by a quote from Alain Bertaud: ‘trying to use minimum housing standards to address a housing shortage is like trying to “solve a famine” by passing a law that everyone must eat 2,000 calories a day, instead of simply producing more food.’

1.4 Lack of understanding of the current situation in London

While there is a clear sense of a national housing crisis, e.g. in the revised National Planning Policy Framework (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2024) which the current government inherits from the previous one, the specific London situation is far less well recognized. In general terms, a recent Competition and Markets Authority study concludes that the house-building sector “is not delivering the number of homes. . . needed” (Competition and Markets Authority, 2024). The official documents also recognizes the “social objective” of ensuring a sufficient number and range of homes for present and future generations. However, despite this extensive attention and policy focus, the actual housing supply in London continues to fall short.

Pre1900	1900-1939	1945-1964	1965-1982	1983-2009	2009-2024
767530	1040470	411520	412500	495850	257870

Figure 1.1 Total Number of Dwellings in London by Period of Construction(1900-2024)

Dwelling Completion	1990-1994	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2019	2020-2024
Private Enterprise	54750	49620	65290	69140	56520	85080	59300
Housing Association	20900	20890	22080	31280	32230	24640	12370
Local Authority	2870	160	190	90	1510	2920	3780

Figure 1.2 Dwelling Completions in London by Tenure Type and Time Period (1990-2024)

The actual housing delivery data (Figure 1.1) suggests a persistent mismatch between stated ambitions and built outcomes. The following analysis is based on housing construction data compiled by the author using official statistics from the Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities, 2024). As shown in housing stock data by period of construction, only around 257,870 dwellings were added between 2009 and 2024—just over half the volume built in the 1983-2009 period (495,850), and less than a quarter of the pre-WWII (1900-1939) total (1,040,470). Meanwhile, disaggregated dwelling completion figures reveal a stark disparity in who builds: local authorities delivered fewer than 4,000 homes in total between 2020 and 2024, compared to over 59,000 by private developers in the same period (Figure 1.2).

While much has been written about London's housing crisis, few studies have systematically examined how the predicament has evolved over the past decade, even less regarding young graduates. The 2011 and 2021 Census is a clear source offering a unique opportunity to investigate whether young graduates are still moving to London (Census on age groups) and whether the housing delivered matches their needs (Census on housing type). The following studies addresses this knowledge gap through a novel study that has not yet been done in the field.

Chapter 2

The Impact of Covid-19 and Shifting Demographics

An analysis of the decade 2011-2021 using Census data does give us a full picture of how the resident population evolved, involving all age cohorts, at very detailed level of geography of London neighbourhoods. However, we note that the year 2021 was a special year in many respects. The decennial Census data was carried amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. With the widespread lockdowns, remote working, and universities' shift to online learning, it is reasonable to expect that a considerable number of university student and recent graduates may have left London and return to their family homes. This raised concerns about whether the 2021 Census might have undercounted the true number of young people residing in London.

To assess this extent, it is useful to compare the Census figure with the Mid-Year Estimates (MYEs). The Census data is based on an actual count on people and their households on Census Day, 21 March 2021 (Office for National Statistics, 2023). In contrast, MYEs are produced annually using detailed demographic models that account for births, deaths, and migration, offering a more realistic estimation of the entire resident population at the mid-point of each year. This MYE is particularly useful to verify the population across all years (i.e. including but not restricted to the Census years). Nevertheless, the MYE is available only at a higher level of geography of boroughs.

In this context, the comparison between 2021 Census and 2021 MYEs has two specific purposes:

- To evaluate the reliability of the Census conducted under COVID-19.
- To see if there is a significant demographic shift over the years.

2.1 Evaluating the Reliability of Census under COVID-19

Figure 2.1 Comparison of 2021 Census and Mid-Year Estimates (2021-2023) by Boroughs

Figure 2.1 compares the 2021 Census with MYEs from 2021, 2022, and 2023 across London's 33 boroughs. The comparison confirms that the 2021 Census figures by borough were close to the 2021 MYE, with a small undercount as expected (since we expect a small number of households did not return their Census forms). There is no substantial deviation that would suggest a very significant undercount or major distortion due to the pandemic, hence the 2021 Census remains a reliable source for our analysis below.

A comparison with the population estimates in 2022 and 2023 show subsequent increase in residential population in all boroughs.

2.2 Structural Shift, Not a Pandemic Glitch

Figure 2.2 Change of Population by Age Band in London, Mid-Year Estimates(2001-2023)

Figure 2.3 Change in Population Share by Age Band in London, Mid-Year Estimates (2001-2023)

Figure 2.2 and Figure 2.3 present age-specific trends from 2001 to 2023, in both absolute numbers and population shares. While the 25-34 age group saw a slight dip in 2021, possibly due to short-term migration or lockdown impacts, the subsequent recovery by 2023 indicates a return to pre-pandemic patterns. However, the long-term trend implies the share of young adults (20-34) has stagnated from 2001 to 2011, and then turned to decline. On the other hand, the 55+ age group have steadily increased in both absolute and proportional terms.

This suggests a structural ageing of London's population—further reinforcing concerns that the city is becoming less accessible to younger generations.

Chapter 3

Spatial Distribution of Young Adults vs. Housing Stock (2011-2021)

Building on the broad demographic trends identified in Chapter 2, this chapter examines the detailed spatial patterns of London's young adult population and the housing stock. While the Census data is compared for all age groups, the analysis is focused on the distribution of the population group aged 20-34 across London in 2011 versus 2021, and in so doing, investigates whether changes in housing supply over that decade did align with the housing needs of this demographic. The analysis has two parts: first, how the geographic concentration of young adults has evolved, and second, how the supply of different types of housing (by number of bedrooms) has changed, and finally how those changes correspond to where young people live. This will highlight whether there is any mismatch between where housing is being added and where young adults aspire to live.

The maps are created at the Lower Layer Super Output Area (LSOA) level, a geographic unit used in UK census data that typically contains around 1,500 residents. The LSOA definition changed for [number] of areas between 2011 and 2021, and my own work following the guidance of ONS (reference) has produced a modified definition that can be used to compare across the years for all areas in London. The bar charts are presented below at the borough level with the boroughs lined up from West London to East London for easy comprehension of the patterns.

Figure 3.1 London Tube Fare Zone Transport for London (2025)

3.1 Age Group 20-24

3.1.1 Overview

The 20-24 age group primarily consists of university students and some new graduates who are at their beginning of careers. We expect that the majority of this group were attending universities, colleges and other further education and their distribution will show patterns that closely align with characteristics of students.

3.1.2 2011 Distribution

Figure 3.2 Share of age 20-24 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

According to the 2011 Census, the 20-24 age bracket predominantly lives in central London (Figure 3.2a). Central areas like Camden and Islington showed relative high concentrations. This extends eastward into Tower Hamlets and Newham, suggesting the distributions are mainly driven by the proximity to major universities (e.g. UCL, LSE, KCL and Queen Mary). In some Zone1 LSOAs, the age bracket accounted for over 30% of the population.

Figure 3.3 Share of 20-24 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

3.1.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021

Figure 3.4 Share of 20-24 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

However, in majority of the boroughs, the 20-24 age bracket saw a slight decrease in population share. The reduction ranges from -0.2% (Hammersmith and Fulham) to -2.5% (Newham) Nevertheless, by comparing Figure 3.2a and Figure 3.2b, a trend of growing concentration in Zone 1 can be seen. This is supported by the borough-level data, where central boroughs like the City of London experienced a 3.8 percentage point increase, followed by smaller gains in Westminster and Kensington & Chelsea (Figure 3.3). This reflects the possible return of young students to family homes during the pandemic, and more importantly how vulnerable they are to short-term shocks such as university closures.

3.2 Age Group 25-34

3.2.1 Overview

This group typically represents young graduates entering employment. In the context of current decade, this cohort largely overlaps with what is commonly referred to as Gen Z. Compared to the 20-24 years old, 25-34 age bracket is considered more mobile and where they live is heavily influenced by where they can find and afford housing.

3.2.2 2011 Distribution

Figure 3.5 Share of age 25-34 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

As expected, their distribution extends beyond the university bubbles and spreads across inner boroughs. Within these areas, the 25-34 age bracket is by far the most dominant, with some LSOAs reaching up to 60% (Figure 3.5a). Significantly, two major clusters emerge: one centred around Wandsworth and another around Tower Hamlets (Figure 3.5b). This suggests a shift from student accommodation to affordable private rentals while employment accessibility remains a key factor.

Figure 3.6 Share of 25-34 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

3.2.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021

Figure 3.7 Share of 25-34 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

By 2021, the share of 25-34-year-olds-now falling within Gen Z's category-had declined in the vast majority of boroughs (Figure 3.7). 29 out of 33 boroughs experienced a drop from -0.2% to -4.5% (Figure 3.6). Unlike the 20-24 cohort, some large decline are also found in the centre boroughs historically favoured by this group, such as Camden(-2.6%), Westminster(-3.1%) and Kensington & Chelsea(-4.5%).

Nevertheless, a few exceptions like the City of London and Havering saw an increase. Significantly, the North Greenwich peninsula stands out with exceptional large gains, with increases reaching up to 60 percentage points. This can be attributed to the Greenwich peninsula development project in 2018 by Allies and Morrison Architects, transforming a post industrial site into a 35,000 people community with 17,500 new homes (Allies and Morrison, 2021). This includes key developments such as the *Upper Riverside* neighbourhood, completed in 2020 by the internationally renowned firm SOM (Greenwich Peninsula, 2025).

3.3 Age Group 35-44

3.3.1 Overview

Compared to younger age groups, the 35-44 year band typically consists of individuals who are more established in their careers, many of them will have a family and may often be homeowners. As such, their residential patterns are less sensitive to short-term disruption and reflects either a transitional, or long-term settlement strategies.

3.3.2 2011 Distribution

Figure 3.8 Share of age 35-44 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Figure 3.9 Share of 35-44 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

The distribution of 35-44 age group shows that most are distributed evenly across London (creffig:SD3a). Most boroughs maintain a similar population share ranging between 13.4% and 17.9%, with Richmond upon Thames and Havering showing the highest and lowest shares respectively (Figure 3.9). This outward shift indicates a wider choice of housing strategies including detached and semi-detached homes. As priorities shift toward space and children’s education, longer commuting distances become more acceptable.

3.3.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021

Figure 3.10 Share of 35-44 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

Between 2011 and 2021, The 35-44 age group exhibits a more balanced variation (Figure 3.10). Slight decreases are found in inner boroughs like Camden and Westminster, while some areas in outer London, for instance, Redbridge and Newham, show minor growth. These changes suggest that this cohort is increasingly favouring outer London locations. Moreover, compared to the younger cohorts, the 35-44 age group appears less vulnerable to housing shocks and more resilient to affordability pressures.

However, this narrative becomes more complex when examining patterns in West Central London—an area typically associated with affluence and high-status residential living. Despite high-profile residential developments in recent years—such as One Hyde Park by Richard Rogers and Battersea Power Station by Frank Gehry, there has been no visible growth in the 35-44 population in these areas—some LSOAs even experienced a 3% to 10% decrease. This could suggest this age group is also being displaced by rapidly rising housing cost, in a market where one-bedroom unit could sell for nearly 7 million (Zoopla Limited, 2025a).

3.4 Age Group 45-54 and 55-64

3.4.1 Overview

The 46-54, and 55-64 age group typically comprises the older, often wealthier class of individuals approaching retirement. This demographic primarily prioritise stability and larger living spaces, making them more inclined to settle in outer rings where detached and semi-detached houses are more abundant.

(a) Share of 45-54 in Resident Population - 2011 (b) Share of 45-54 in Resident Population - 2021

(c) Share of 55-64 in Resident Population - 2011 (d) Share of 55-64 in Resident Population - 2021

Figure 3.11

3.4.2 2011 Distribution

The distribution of middle-aged groups (45-54) follows an outward trend, yet remains quite evenly distributed towards outer edges of London. The proportion in most areas falls within the range of 10-20%, with some concentrations start to emerge in Bromley, Croydon, and Barnet. The 55-64 cohort continues this outward migration pattern but with significantly

lower representation in inner boroughs ranging 5% to 10%. The gradual outward movement from 45-64 highlights their preference of residing in the outer boroughs.

Figure 3.12 Share of 45-54 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

Figure 3.13 Share of 55-64 in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

3.4.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021

Figure 3.14 Share of 45-54 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

Figure 3.15 Share of 55-64 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

Contrary to the typical assumption of outward migration, the 2021 Census reveals that both age brackets experienced modest yet widely distributed increase across London, notably, the Share of 54-65 increase among 32 out of 33 boroughs in London (Figure 3.13). However, as shown in Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15, it is also worth mentioning that most of the changes for both cohorts lies within $\pm 10\%$, indicating a gradual and steady ageing of the population across London.

3.5 Age 65 and Above

3.5.1 Overview

As this group of people primarily consist of the retirees with more established living arrangements, they exhibit lower mobility and are more likely to remain in permanent homes. Their distribution patterns are often shaped by health service accessibility, proximity to family, and

overall quality of the living environment, given that this tends to be the wealthiest group overall.

Figure 3.16 Share of 65+ in Resident Population (a) 2011 (b) 2021

3.5.2 2011 Distribution

The distribution of the 65+ age group inverts from to the young generations (20-34): there is virtually a void in the city centre and they concentrate heavily in outer London. In inner boroughs, most areas have proportions below 8%. However, the highest gatherings, with some LSOAs exceeding 25%, are found in Havering, Bromley and Harrow (Figure 3.16a). This pattern is likely to be shaped by long-term home ownership, quieter environments, and better access to suburban healthcare and community services.

Figure 3.17 Share of 65+ in Resident Population by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

3.5.3 Patterns and Changes in 2021

The 2021 Census reveals a clear and gradual intensification of this pattern. The share of 65+ residents increased in 31 out of 33 boroughs (Figure 3.17), with borough-level gains ranging mostly between 0.3% and 2.6%. As shown in Figure 3.18, increases are observed in outer London; the increases in central boroughs are generally smaller; the overall growth remains widespread. Most of these changes fall within $\pm 10\%$, supporting the idea that a continued and broad-based ageing trend is sweeping across the capital.

Figure 3.18 Share of 65+ in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021

Figure 3.19 Comparison on Share of Different Age Groups - Difference 2011-2021

Younger cohorts (20-34) decline in most boroughs while older age groups (35 and above) show consistent, borough-wide increases

Chapter 4

Can London still accommodate young people with suitable housing?

Although London's younger groups shrink in size and percentage share amid population aging nationally, as a vibrant world city the share of young graduates in the city is expected to remain high both for the sake of the UK and for retaining the best learning opportunities for young graduates. An example of retaining a vibrant capital city within significant national population decline and aging is Tokyo metropolitan area (Xu et al., 2024). The slight decline of young adult numbers may also be a COVID lockdown effect, and their numbers are starting to recover. Hence a cogent question arises: whether the city is building the right kinds of homes in the right places for the young graduates?

4.1 One-Bedroom Units 2011

Figure 4.1 Share of 1-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Being the most mobile and price-conscious cohort, the 25-34 Age Group would mostly prefer small (one- or two-bedroom dwellings) when moving into the city. Similarly, for reasons of privacy, they would prefer not to share dwellings if they can avoid it.

Figure 4.2 Share of 1-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

Single bedroom units are primarily found in central London: Westminster, Kensington & Chelsea, Islington and Camden. This centric distribution is particularly obvious in the City of London, where it accounts for more than a half. However, in most other boroughs, 1-bedroom units' proportion remains relatively low, generally below 20% (Figure 4.2).

4.2 Spatial Misalignment for 1-bedroom Units

(a) Share of 20-24 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021
 (b) Share of 1-Bedroom in All Households - Difference 2011-2021

Figure 4.3

The 2021 maps (Figure 4.1b) and borough-level bar charts (Figure 4.2) together reveal that the share of one bedroom flat has, in effect, declined across much of London over the decade. Figure 4.3b highlights that there is certain increase in East Central London, particularly around the Greenwich peninsular, which aligns with the major growth of 25-34 age group (Figure 4.3a). However, for the most part, increases in one-bedroom units are either limited, or simply occur in the wrong locations. Comparing Figure 4.3a and Figure 4.3b, it is not hard to see the 25-34 Age Group population have grown in outer East London, yet counter-intuitively the supply of one-bedroom units in those areas has remained stagnant or even declined. Conversely, there are major reductions of this age group in West London, yet the supply of one-bedroom dwellings continued to increase, in some cases ranging from 10% to 40% percentage point.

4.3 Two-Bedroom Units in 2011

Figure 4.4 Share of 2-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Two-Bedroom remains a good choice for young couples or small families, or those seeking flat-sharing arrangements within this 25-34 Age Group. The properties are more evenly distributed across both inner and outer boroughs, making them the most evenly distributed housing type in London. (Figure 4.4a). Their proportion ranges from 24% in Harrow to 42% in Tower Hamlets, indicating their widespread availability. The balanced distribution suggests two-bedroom units could serve as a transitional stage that accommodates not only young professionals but also small families.

4.4 Limited Alignment with 25-34

Figure 4.5 Share of 2-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

(a) Share of 25-34 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021 (b) Share of 2-Bedroom in All Households - Difference 2011-2021

Figure 4.6

Two-bedroom properties experienced a mixture of increases and decreases across central London at the LSOA level, which, when aggregated, resulted in minimal change at the borough level (Figure 4.5). The largest change was a modest -1.7% in Richmond upon Thames. In Outer London, however, most LSOAs recorded a general decline. Figure 4.6b further illustrates that the few notable increases in two-bedroom units tend to be scattered and isolated, showing little alignment with the spatial patterns of the 25-34 age group's migration. (Figure 4.6a)

4.5 Three-Bedroom Units in 2011

Figure 4.7 Share of 3-Bedroom in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Figure 4.8 Share of 3-Bedroom Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

Figure 4.9 Share of 3-Bedroom in All Households- Difference 2011-2021

Three-bedroom homes have traditionally served larger families and are predominantly located in outer London boroughs. This type of property dominates the outer ring of London, and Figure 4.8 indicates that the highest proportions of three-bedroom homes are found in boroughs such as Havering(49.6%), Bexley(45.7%). The prevalence of these larger properties in outer rings aligns with the older age groups' decentralisation, who are more likely to seek permanent housing solutions.

4.6 Four and more Bedroom Units

Figure 4.10 Share of 4 and More Bedrooms in All Households (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Figure 4.11 Share of 4 and More Bedrooms Dwellings in All Households by Boroughs - 2011 and 2021

Multi-bedroom units-typically four bedrooms or more-are most suitable for large families, intergenerational households, or elderly residents who have aged in place. In 2011, these properties were overwhelmingly located in the outer boroughs, forming clear clusters across North and South London, particularly in Barnet, Bromley, and Croydon (Figure 4.10a). Their presence was minimal in central boroughs, where high-density, smaller units dominate. Interestingly, the spatial pattern of these homes mirrors the distribution of the 65+ age group, suggesting these units serve long-term residents more than incoming young adults.

4.7 Good News? Lots of 4-beds are built

(a) Share of 25-34 in Resident Population - Difference 2011-2021 (b) Share of 4 and More Bedrooms in All Households - Difference 2011-2021

Figure 4.12

By 2021, every borough saw a noticeable increase in the proportion of these large homes (Figure 4.11), making them the only housing category with across-the-board growth. We could see major increase in outer-ring London. These additions appear more tailored for the older population groups than the influx of younger residents. The locations of these four-bedroom increases align poorly with 25-34 age band emerging geographies, offering little support for the kinds of housing young adults might actually need.(Figure 4.12b). There is 3.6% increase in Havering-a place where 25-34 years old have shown an increase-and none of the other house-types can address the problem. So, the good news for Gen Z is that they can now possibly share in a 4-bedroom houses in Zone 6 (Figure 3.1).

Figure 4.13 Comparison on Share of Different Households - Difference 2011-2021

Across London boroughs, the supply of smaller homes declined or stagnated, while larger, family-sized properties-ironically less relevant to Gen Z-saw increases.

Chapter 5

Structural Failures in London's Housing Market for the New Generation

The evidence of the previous chapters reveals a troubling finding that London's housing supply appears to be following the money (of the wealthier, older families) rather than the aspirations of young graduates (who are arguably the very future for the city). On the one hand, there is the geo-demographic shifts (a declining of youth share in the most affluent parts of London, where the young graduates are likely to find the best jobs), and on the other hand, there is a housing supply mismatch (few affordable small homes, plenty of large ones, especially in the most attractive parts of the city to the young graduates). These worrying trends appear to be symptoms of deeper, structural and systemic issues. This chapter dissects these failures and explores what they mean from the perspective of future young architects. The chapter will also investigate how young graduates are coping today in London through case studies on the ground.

5.1 Self-Regulated Market v.s. Social Needs

One fundamental issue is the over reliance on market-driven housing delivery, assuming that if the demand for housing is high, developers will build enough houses to meet that demand. However, the developers often choose to build luxury or upscale housing to maximize returns, rather than the types of housing that are most needed. For example, Bishops Avenue in North London - also known as "Billionaires Row" - dramatically illustrates the market's skewed priorities. The street was revealed to have £350m worth of luxury properties left vacant

(Booth, 2014). The avenue was ranked the second most expensive street in London, attracting billionaire buyers from the Middle East, Russia and China, yet 95% of them do not really live in the place. Currently, those mansions are left empty and fallen into serious disrepair. Such blatant neglect by the wealthy-is like treating housing assets as carelessly as parked luxury cars left to decay. Meanwhile, Britain faces a national shortage of around 100,000 homes per year in supply (Booth, 2014). The tendency to build the wrong houses to maximize profit is also observed in history. For example, in the 1980s much of the limited development that did occur shifted toward sheltered housing for the elderly (especially for older owner-occupiers), while construction of homes for families by local authorities was sharply cut back (Malpass, 2005). The pattern remains true today. We see many examples from the massive-built 4-bedrooms houses in outer London, to One Hyde Park or the Battersea Power Station: The market on its own has no incentive to provide housing at a price point that newly graduated nurses, teachers, or architects can afford. In conclusion, one lesson for the young architect is that the market-driven approach tends to serve wealth over need. As future practitioners, they must strive to create housing solutions that are not only economically viable but also socially responsive.

5.2 Policy and Planning Shortcomings

Another problem lies within London's planning framework and housing policy. Chapter 1 already mentioned neither the Right to Buy Policies nor the Help to Buy Policies has delivered the desired supply to the needed people. Instead, those policies are rather short-sighted and have created an increasing burden to the later generations. Beyond these specific policies, the general retreat of the state from housebuilding has also been a structural failure. There has been a long-term shift towards relying on private developers to build homes, while public authorities largely "manage" planning permissions and targets. Developers, as mentioned, commonly use a "build-to-sell" model timed to not flood the market, where they release new units slowly to avoid saturating supply at any given time. This strategy ensures that property prices (and thus profits) stay high, but it also means chronic under-supply. Hall and Ward (2014) note that in some cases it is more profitable to own land than build on it. They also reference the research from Bramley et al. (2010), showing boosting the supply of affordable social housing would reduce unmet housing need far more effectively than the same increase in private housing supply. For instance, the study found that adding 269,000 social dwellings could reduce housing need by 168,000 households, whereas adding 435,000 private homes would cut need by only 91,000 (Hall and Ward, 2014). Despite evidence like this, the UK has

persistently underinvested in social housing. As noted earlier, only about 1,148 social units out of 377,00 new homes are completed per year in London in recent times. (Barber, 2024)

In summary, London's policy and planning landscape has, despite good intentions, failed to deliver an adequate affordable housing. Another valuable lesson for young architects is that policy and planning are as crucial as design in shaping housing outcomes. Young professionals in architecture and urban design must understand the housing policy and their delivery system, realizing it is the overall structure - not solely the developer or the state - that is to blame in this massive housing crisis.

5.3 Bottlenecks in the planning process

Several external factors in recent years have further complicated housing delivery in London aside from market and policy issues. This includes space standards introduced to ensure quality but reducing the total number of units built, and London has effectively chosen to keep these standards mostly voluntary to avoid choking supply. Yet supply has been choked anyway by other factors. For example, new regulations introduced in the wake of the Grenfell disaster, along with more stringent environmental and safety requirements, have significantly increased construction costs (Competition and Markets Authority, 2024). This means the young generation have gotten the worst of both worlds: not enough homes, and some that are still too small or poor in quality.

Local opposition to development the 'Nimby' or 'Not in My Back Yard' phenomenon, is another barrier. Attempts to densify suburbs or build new housing in well-off areas often face resistance from existing residents, which slows or downsizes projects. The young would-be residents who do not yet live in those neighbourhoods have no voice in these local planning battles, and hence, the planning system usually ends up representing the older housed community.

Future architects should certainly embrace higher safety and environmental standards. However, they can also work on the cost-effective design solutions. Regarding community opposition, architects may develop skills in community engagement at an early design stage, showing residents how the design minimizes the negative impacts and brings benefits, thus making the housing structure more inclusive to young cohorts.

5.4 Consequences: Young Londoners' Coping Strategies

Faced with these affordability challenges, how are young Londoners responding on the ground? Kichanova (2019) identified three common housing strategies among young professionals in London: stretching, cramming and leaving.

Stretching: Some people choose to move farther away from the city centre, sacrificing commute time in exchange for more affordable rent and larger space.

Cramming: Others opt for shared housing in central areas, sacrificing privacy and personal space while needing to cope with challenges related to cohabiting with strangers.

Leaving: For those who are unable to find a sustainable balance, the last option is to leave altogether by relocating to other UK cities or even moving abroad in search of better affordability and quality of life. While the three methods above certainly have their drawbacks, Kichanova identified a fourth living style that has started to gain popularity among young people: Micro-Housing. The British Property Federation and JLL (2018) defines Micro-Housing as apartments with sizes ranging from 20 to 40 square metres, and can be self-contained or encompass shared amenities. However, despite such variations, micro-housing developments generally sit on three pillars of convenience and privacy.

(a) Exterior of The Collective Old Oak co-living development in West London (The Collective, 2024)
 (b) Shared laundry and lounge space within The Collective Old Oak (The Collective, 2024)

Figure 5.1 Share of age 35-44 in Resident Population (a) 2011, (b) 2021.

Figure 5.2 Typical 12 sqm studio layout at The Collective Old Oak (The Collective, 2024)

Case Study: The Collective Old Oak A notable example of Micro-Housing is the Collective Old Oak in London, which became the largest micro-living scheme in Europe at its completion in 2016. The development provides fully furnished en-suite rooms with shared communal facilities, designed to offer a more affordable and flexible housing solution for young professionals. Strategically located five minutes from Old Oak Common Station, The Collective Old Oak benefits from its proximity to a major transport hub, making it attractive to commuters and transient professionals. The station, which is expected to be completed in the early 2030s, will serve as a key transport hub in West London, connecting the HS2, the Great Western Railway, the Elizabeth Line and the Heathrow Express, with an estimated 250,000 passengers per day (HS2, 2025) —four times the current volume of London Kings Cross Station (RailwayData, 2024).

Micro-Housing or Co-Housing - In both micro-housing and co-housing, residents share kitchens and other living spaces in a highly communal setting. This has often led to the misconception that these two housing strategies are equivalent. In fact, micro-housing and co-housing are designed for two different types of individuals. Co-Living often encourages social interaction through the design of circulation and the sharing of common spaces. This will appeal to those who seek a sense of community. However, for those who prioritise privacy, such design can lead to discomfort, and they may feel pressured to socialise. Kichanova (2019) suggests that the co-living arrangement, instead of fostering belonging, can actually backfire by causing loneliness and insecurity through forcing barely known strangers to share spaces. In contrast, even though micro-housing will still inevitably require sharing spaces due to spatial constraints, there is much less emphasis on social interaction.

How suitable is the Collective Old Oak for the wider city? - The location of the development in Zone 3 offers a trade-off between affordability and connectivity. While it is not located in the city centre, its proximity to a major transportation hub makes commuting efficient and accessible. Currently, residents can arrive at Paddington Station within 30 minutes, and by 2030, with further integration of Old Oak station into key transport networks, accessibility is expected to improve further. According to Lord Hendy of Richmond Hill, Minister of State for Transport, passengers will be able to travel from Birmingham to the Old Oak station in 40 minutes, and can then arrive at Euston in 6 minutes, though the exact schedules are yet to be confirmed. (TheyWorkForYou, 2024).

Despite offering a comparatively lower-cost alternative to traditional renting, the Collective Old Oak is still financially demanding for many young renters. The development offers three tiers of en-suite accommodation, with rents ranging from £1,299 to £1,950 per month. By contrast, the average rent in the Hammersmith and Fulham area has increased to £2,693 per month, with the cost of a one-bedroom apartment averaging at £1,903 per month (Office for National Statistics, 2025b). However, the Collective Old Oak's prices remain a substantial burden for young renters. Taking the average year earnings (£35,386) for individuals aged 22-29 in London (Office for National Statistics, 2024), even the lowest-tier accommodation at the Collective Old Oak would require tenants to allocate 44% of their annual income to rent.

Therefore, micro-housing is not a universal solution for every young graduates, nor does it provide a solution for the structural issues of housing supply and long-term accessibility of housing. Micro-housing rents are still overly expensive for a large number of young adults.

Figure 5.3 View of World's End Estate in Chelsea, London

Figure 5.4 Plan of 1, 2, 3 bedroom flats in World's End Estate (Zoopla Limited, 2025b)

Case Studies: World's End Estate World's End Estate (Figure 5.3) was a mass social housing project in Chelsea by architect Eric Lyons and Jim Cadbury-Brown (Architecture Review, 1977) It was born out of slum clearance of Victorian terraced houses in 1970s: 830 houses has been pulled down and 744 new homes - accommodating 500 people - were proposed (Architects' Journal, 1977). Although the project was proclaimed as "village style living in the heart of London", Lyon's plan for 250 people per acre was once rejected by London County Council for being far above its limit of 136 people per acre (Municipal Dreams, 2024). This was fought back by Chelsea council, arguing only such arrangement would rehouse all the displaced people from the slum clearance. (Municipal Dreams, 2024) Lyon's plan was later approved, featuring seven high-rise tower blocks (18-21 storeys) interconnected by lower-rise blocks and walkways. Inside the estate, the dwelling contains a mix of unit types, ranging from studios and 1-bedroom flats to larger 4-bedroom maisonettes to accommodate various sizes of households (Municipal Dreams, 2024). In this sense, the social objective (housing everyone) was prioritized over strict adherence to density norms.

Comparison on Space Standards - Because World's End predates the 2010/2015 space standards, many of its flats would not meet today's minimum sizes or layouts as dictated by London Housing Design Guide. However, it is worth considering the trade-offs in the design because:

- The point of the studies is only to provide an example of council housing that does not completely comply with the current regulation yet has proved to be successful.
- The 2010 London Housing Design Guide clearly enumerates requirements for different types of spaces.
- The criteria of minimum space standards have either stayed the same or become less demanding over time, so what conformed to the 1970 standards should still comply with the current standards.

Room/Standard	GIA(sq _m)	Built-in Storage(sq _m)	Hallway Width(m)	Living, Dining and Kitchen Spaces(sq _m)	Width of Seating Area(sq _m)	Number of Living Spaces	External Windows in Living Spaces	Bedroom Area(sq _m)	Balconies Depth/Width(m)
1b1p	46.6	1.7	1.4	24.5	5.1	1	Yes	12.0	-
1b2p	46.6	1.7	1.4	24.5	5.1	1	Yes	12.0	-
2b3p	74.2	2.0	0.85	33.9	4.9	1	Yes	10.2/10.3	2.8/3.0
2b4p	74.2	2.0	0.85	33.9	4.9	1	Yes	10.2/10.3	2.8/3.0
3b4p	90.9	2.0	0.73	28.2	3.1	1	Yes	9.3/10.0/12.9	1.4/2.7
3b5p	90.9	3.5	0.73	28.2	3.1	1	Yes	9.3/10.0/12.9	1.4/2.7
3b6p	90.9	3.5	0.73	28.2	3.1	1	Yes	9.3/10.0/12.9	1.4/2.7

Figure 5.5 Comparison on different house types in World's End Estate and London Housing Guide (Mayor of London, 2010). (Units not meeting modern standards are marked in red. Data based on real-estate listings.)

This suggests that, while most of the criteria fall above the London Housing Guide, some larger apartments feature smaller hallways, limited living space and constrained bedroom areas. For instance, although London Housing Guide requires that a minimum living space for 6 people should be 31 m², the actual number for the 3-bedrooms stays at 28.2 m² - even lower than that of 2-bedroom flat (London Development Agency, 2010).

Early reviews of the estate were harsh. Architecture Review (1977) commented “‘As a nice place to living in’, it fails”; the irregular internal spaces were further described using words like “odd” and “dark and squalid”; the previous Victorian Slums on the site was compared as offering greater “human dignity”.

However, 30 years later, the Building Design Magazine (2008) described it as “Living Proof of Success”. The Magazine re-exams how the residents had adapted after 30 years in residence. Obviously, the residents are finding it like a home. The “irregular balconies” criticized by the Architecture Review was commented from the residents as

“Each of the tower flats had a small balcony. Last summer it was de rigueur to block up the outlet, fill up the water to the threshold level and there was a small paddling pool for the kids just outside the 20th storey living room window.” They continued “I like the unusual and quirky design a lot” and “It’s awkward for fitting furniture but infinitely more interesting than your average council block”

We have to admit that the high-density tower block solution is not the solution in the current housing, but its lesson for the young architect is, first, that it shows that rigid standards are not the only path to a successful living environment - a design that bends some rules can still foster strong community and resident satisfaction, given time and adaptation. It also illustrates the importance of evaluating architecture not just by drawings or regulations, but by how it works for people over decades.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

Addressing London's housing structural failure requires action on multiple fronts - no single change will be sufficient for this complex problem. This chapter discusses a range of strategies that could be applied to alleviate the crisis and make the city more accommodating for the next generation of young graduates.

6.1 Potential interventions for a more responsive housing system

Bramley et al. (2010) research reveals the superiority of building more council housing over private housing in relation to catering the unmet housing need. Therefore, one would naturally think constructing new social homes directly benefits the young graduates and future generations who cannot afford market prices. Confidence is given by a history of councils' ability to deliver them at scale - over 5 million council homes were built in the UK between 1949 and 1980 (UK Parliament, 2025).

However, we must admit there are other aspects that complicate this demand and supply issue. One argument is that the provision of housing might be circular like building new roads: the more we provide, the greater the demand. Holmans (2013) studies concludes that this mainly happens at local rather than national level. That being said, in some communities, the supply of new housing may simply be occupied by more affluent in-migrants (Hall and Ward, 2014). Therefore, one general solution will be a more careful approach to the planning of social houses, both centrally and regionally. For example, the government must first realize

how much the shortages of the housing, and thus provide a strategic plan in a national level. Below this level, the local councils may then create sub-regional plan that builds the right number of houses and right type of houses in the right spaces.

A further key issue is that the expansion of social housing is restrained by land availability. Historically, governments and public development entities systematically allocated their land reserves for both private and social housing projects without implementing replenishment mechanisms for these public land inventories. This legacy has left housing associations dependent on acquiring land at inflated market rates to develop social housing (Hall and Ward, 2014). Regeneration of brown field sites and the conversion of redundant commercial space gain importance.

London's development is physically constrained by its Green Belt - a ring of protected open land around the city. A nuanced reform of Green Belt policies could alleviate some structural pressure. This does not mean wholesale elimination of green belts, but a careful review to identify low-value or poorly utilized land that could be released for sustainable housing development. For instance, pockets of land around transport nodes on the city's edge that are technically "green belt" but perhaps of low environmental quality could be re-designated for high-density, transit-oriented development focused on affordable housing. Llewelyn-Davies Planning, who are commissioned to maximize the use of brownfield sites found that such places might provide for between 52,000 and 106,000 new homes in London. (Hall and Ward, 2014)

Another potential direction is the conversion of other types of buildings. With changing work patterns (especially post-COVID), London now has a significant amount of under-utilized office buildings. Recent data show that about 9% of London's offices are sitting vacant, with vacancy rates as high as 20% in some areas like Hammersmith (Kollewe, 2025). Converting even a portion of this space could yield tens of thousands of new housing units without consuming new land.

To be fair, the above policy considerations are being debated in the policy arena in general terms with affordable housing being targeted to vulnerable groups like the unemployed, the long term sick and disabled. The policy conversations are almost entirely blind to the predicaments of the young graduates, who are expected to fend for themselves. There is currently little sense of what help they need. This is why the research findings revealed by this dissertation is cogent for further policy development.

6.2 Summary and future work

The research findings reveal a very disturbing picture: London's current housing system is failing to accommodate its new generation of young graduates. Chapter 1 showed that despite a long history of housing reform, today's young graduate faces unprecedented affordability challenges. Chapter 2 revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic had only a transient effect on where young adults live, and the deeper trend is a structural ageing of the city's population, which has not been seen since post WWII. Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 highlighted a clear misalignment between housing supply and young Londoners' needs and London is largely building the wrong types of housing in the wrong locations for the next generation of workers. If the status quo persists, London may risk a growing exodus of young talent. To avoid such a future, both policymakers and architects must take decisive action. Policymakers must reshape housing supply—expanding affordable and social housing, enforcing affordability quotas, and reforming planning policies with the added focus on the young graduates. History shows that the market alone favours wealth over need; public intervention is essential to support young renters and buyers. Architects, in turn, must respond with inclusive, innovative, and economical designs. Together, planners and designers must ensure London builds not just more homes, but the right homes for its next generation of workers.

References

- 9B Careers (2025). Architectural salary guide. <https://www.9bcareers.com/career-support/salary-guide.aspx> [retrieved 28 Feb 2025].
- Allies and Morrison (2021). Greenwich peninsula masterplan. <https://www.alliesandmorrison.com/projects/greenwich-peninsula-masterplan/> [retrieved 27 March 2025].
- Architects' Journal (1977). World's end estate, chelsea. *Architects' Journal*. https://www.worlds-end.org.uk/files/Architects_Journal_-_April_1977.pdf [retrieved 25 March 2025].
- Architecture Review (1977). End of the road. *Architecture Review*.
- Barber, O. (2024). Mayor of london oversees just 71 completions under the current ahp in first quarter of 2024/25. *Housing Today*. <https://www.housingtoday.co.uk/news/mayor-of-london-oversees-just-71-completions-under-the-current-ahp-in-first-quarter-of-2024/25/5131039.article?> [retrieved 4 April 2025].
- Booth, R. (2014). Inside 'billionaires row': London's rotting, derelict mansions worth £350m. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2014/jan/31/inside-london-billionaires-row-derelict-mansions-hampstead> [retrieved 31 March 2025].
- Borrett, A. (2024). Does gen z have it tougher than previous generations? *Financial Times*. <https://www.ft.com/content/db076232-b674-485b-8693-a575caae4f06> [retrieved 4 Nov 2024].
- Bramley, B., Pawson, H., White, M., Watkins, D., and Pleace, N. (2010). Estimating housing need. *DCLG*.
- Bratley, M. (2024). Bank of mum & dad: 9 million brits receive 'lump sums' of money from parents... but how does it really affect their finances? *IFA Magazine*.
- British Property Federation and JLL (2018). Micro living defined.
- Building Design Magazine (2008). Living proof of success. *Building Design Magazine*. https://www.worlds-end.org.uk/files/Building_Design_-_November_2008.pdf [retrieved 3 March 2025].
- Competition and Markets Authority (2024). Housebuilding market study: final report. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/housebuilding-market-study-final-report> [retrieved 1 April 2025].

- Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (2024). Live tables on house building. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/live-tables-on-house-building> [retrieved 11 April 2024].
- Greater London Authority (2014). Nationally described space standard - technical requirements. *Greater London Authority*.
- Greenwich Peninsula (2025). Greenwich peninsula masterplan. <https://www.greenwichpeninsula.co.uk/the-peninsulist/the-masterplan/> [retrieved 28 March 2025].
- Hall, P. and Ward, C. (2014). *Sociable cities: The 21st-century reinvention of the garden city*. Routledge, 2 edition.
- Holmans, A. (2013). New estimates of housing demand and need in England, 2011 to 2031. *Town and Country Planning, Tomorrow Series*.
- HS2 (2025). Old oak common - hs2. *HS2*. <https://www.hs2.org.uk/building-hs2/stations/old-oak-common/> [retrieved 23 March 2025].
- Imperial College (2025). Accommodation guarantee. <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/students/accommodation/prospective/ug/how-to-apply/accommodation-guarantee/> [retrieved 30 March 2025].
- John, J. (2025). Most gen z say bank of mum and dad gifts come ‘with strings attached’. *Financial Times*. https://www.ft.com/content/62e82137-a382-4ea1-bf57-92411ac6ff8a?utm_source=share-button [retrieved 25 Jan 2025].
- Kichanova, V. (2019). Size doesn't matter. *Adam Smith Institute*.
- Kollewe, J. (2025). Office-to-homes conversions: London blocks hold fresh allure since shift to home-working. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2025/jan/05/office-to-homes-conversions-london-blocks-hold-fresh-allure-since-shift-to-home-working> [retrieved 2 April 2025].
- London Development Agency (2010). London housing design guide: Interim edition. London: Design for London. *London Development Agency*. http://www.designforlondon.gov.uk/uploads/media/Interim_London_Housing_Design_Guide.pdf Architects [retrieved 17 March 2025].
- Malpass, P. (2005). *The Housing Crisis*. London: Croom Helm. Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Mayor of London (2010). London housing design guide. *London Development Agency*.
- Mayor of London (2023). Housing design standards. *London Plan Guidance*.
- McCallum, C. (2024). Cost of living in London: Your simple guide. *HomeViews*. https://www.homeviews.com/blog/cost-of-living-in-london-your-simple-guide?utm_source=share-button [retrieved 13 Feb 2025].
- Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government (2024). National planning policy framework. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/67aafe8f3b41f783cca46251/NPPF_December_2024.pdf [retrieved 11 April 2024].

- Municipal Dreams (2024). The world's end estate, chelsea: 'village style living in the heart of london.'. *WordPress*. <https://municipaldreams.wordpress.com/2013/10/29/the-worlds-end-estate-chelsea-village-style-living-in-the-heart-of-london/> [retrieved 27 March 2025].
- New Economics Foundation (2024). More than 4 in 10 council homes sold under right to buy now owned by private landlords. *New Economics Foundation*. <https://neweconomics.org/2024/05/more-than-4-in-10-council-homes-sold-under-right-to-buy-now-owned-by-private-landlords> [retrieved 2 April 2025].
- Office for National Statistics (2023). Measurements used in census 2021 data. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/census/census2021dictionary/measurementsusedincensus2021data> [retrieved 26 March 2025].
- Office for National Statistics (2024). Earnings and hours worked, uk region by age group. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/earningsandworkinghours/datasets/earningsandhoursworkedukregionbyagegroup> [retrieved 3 Feb 2025].
- Office for National Statistics (2025a). Average weekly earnings in great britain: January 2025. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/bulletins/averageweeklyearningsingreatbritain/january2025> [retrieved 11 Feb 2025].
- Office for National Statistics (2025b). Private rent and house prices, uk: February 2025. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/inflationandpriceindices/bulletins/privaterentandhousepricesuk/february2025> [retrieved 15 Feb 2025].
- Palate, S. (2020). Towards a deregulated domesticity: The making of 'homes for today and tomorrow'. PhD thesis, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom.
- RailwayData (2024). London kings cross station. *RailwayData*. <https://www.railwaydata.co.uk/stations/overview/?TLC=KGX> [retrieved 17 March 2025].
- Scanlon, K., Blanc, F., Edge, A., and Whitehead, C. (2019). The bank of mum and dad: How it really works. *Report for Family Building Society, LSE, London*.
- Spratt, V. (2024). The housing crisis means adulthood starts at 35 for gen z. *The Independent*. <https://inews.co.uk/news/house-crisis-reshape-adulthood-gen-z-2857324> [retrieved 2 April 2025].
- Students' Union UCL (2024). Finding emergency accommodation. <https://studentsunionucl.org/finding-emergency-accommodation> [retrieved 13 Dec 2024].
- The Collective (2024). Old oak. <https://www.thecollective.com/locations/old-oak> [retrieved 11 April 2024].
- TheyWorkForYou (2024). High speed 2 line: Old oak common station. *TheyWorkForYou*. <https://www.theyworkforyou.com/wrans/?id=2024-11-11.HL2382.h> [retrieved 24 March 2025].

- UCL (2024). Applying for ucl accommodation. <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/accommodation/prospective-residents> [retrieved 13 Dec 2024].
- UK Parliament (2025). Build it up, sell it off. <https://www.parliament.uk/business/publications/research/olympic-britain/housing-and-home-life/build-it-up-sell-it-off/> [retrieved 2 April 2025].
- Wolf, M. (2013). Buyers beware of britain’s absurd property trap. *Financial Times*. <http://www.ft.com/content/aa1c9dfa-30ea-11e3-b478-00144feab7de> [retrieved 2 April 2025].
- Xu, X., Ma, J., Sho, K., and Seta, F. (2024). Are east asian “shrinking cities” falling into a loop? insights from the interplay between population decline and metropolitan concentration in japan. *Cities*, 155:105445.
- Zoopla Limited (2025a). 1 bed flat for sale. <https://www.zoopla.co.uk/for-sale/details/66687083/> [retrieved 3 April 2025].
- Zoopla Limited (2025b). World’s end estate. <https://www.zoopla.co.uk/for-sale/property/london/worlds-end-estate/berenger-walk/> [retrieved 3 April 2025].